

TRIGONOMETRIC IDENTITIES OF THE QUADRILATERAL

Sh.L.Ermatov

Andijan State University.

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It is known that there are many trigonometric identities regarding the Triangle. These mirrors represent the trigonometric relationship between the inner corners of a triangle, the trigonometric relationship between the inner corners of the Triangle and its main elements (surface, perimeter, sides, radius of the inner and outer drawn circle, bisector, median, height). A similar case applies to a quadrilateral, that is, it is possible to indicate a trigonometric relationship between the inner corners and the main elements of the quadrilateral. These identities are known to be four times less in triangular identities. We bring some of them. Let an arbitrary convex quadrilateral be drawn internally into the circle (Figure 1). The tip of the central corner of the circle O if at the point, then $\angle COD = 2\alpha$, $\angle AOD = 2\beta$, $\angle AOB = 2\gamma$, $\angle COB = 2\delta$, $\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta = \pi$. Then the area of a quadrilateral consists of the sum of the areas of the four triangles:

$$S = \frac{1}{2}R^2(\sin 2\alpha + \sin 2\beta + \sin 2\gamma + \sin 2\delta) \quad (1)$$

On the other hand

$$S = S_{ABC} + S_{CDA} = 2R^2(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \gamma \cdot \sin(\alpha + \beta) + \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \beta \cdot \sin(\gamma + \delta));$$

$$S = S_{BCD} + S_{ABD} = 2R^2(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \sin(\gamma + \beta) + \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \beta \cdot \sin(\alpha + \delta)).$$

Arayp $\alpha + \beta = \pi - \gamma - \delta$ va $\gamma + \beta = \pi - \alpha - \delta$ considering the fact that. Then the surface is

$$S = 2R^2 \sin(\alpha + \beta)(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \gamma + \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \beta);$$

$$S = 2R^2 \sin(\gamma + \beta)(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \alpha + \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \beta).$$

We equate these expressions to each other and after the trigonometric form substitutions we obtain the first trigonometric mirror to the quadrilateral:

$$2(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \gamma + \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \beta) = \cos(\gamma - \delta) - \cos(\gamma + \delta) + \cos(\alpha + \beta) - \cos(\alpha - \beta) =$$

$$= 2 \cos \frac{\gamma - \delta + \alpha - \beta}{2} \cdot \cos \frac{\gamma - \delta - \alpha + \beta}{2} = 2 \cos \frac{2\gamma + 2\alpha - \pi}{2} \cdot \frac{2\gamma + 2\beta - \pi}{2}.$$

As a result, the formula for the area of the rectangle comes to the following appearance:

$$S = 2R^2 \sin(\alpha + \beta) \cdot \sin(\alpha + \gamma) \cdot \sin(\gamma + \beta) = 2R^2 \sin B \cdot \sin C \cdot \sin \varphi \quad (2)$$

This formula states that between two angles and diagonals of a quadrilateral φ the corner is involved. Comparing the last formula with (1), we obtain the two main trigonometric identities of the quadrilateral:

$$\sin 2\alpha + \sin 2\beta + \sin 2\gamma + \sin 2\delta = 4\sin(\alpha + \beta) \cdot \sin(\beta + \gamma) \cdot \sin(\gamma + \alpha);$$

$$\sin(\alpha + \beta)(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \gamma + \sin \alpha \cdot \sin \beta) = \sin(\gamma + \beta)(\sin \delta \cdot \sin \alpha + \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \beta).$$

In contrast to cases where the angles in the mirrors formed for a rectangle are the inner corners of the Triangle in the mirrors for a triangle, they are the corners of the rectangle whose sides are visible from the arc of the circle. The main thing is that as the Formula (1) and (2) applies to a circle for rectangles drawn internally, the trigonometric identities generated by them are also subject to this condition. By introducing changes in shape substitutions and angles, we obtain another trigonometric mirror:

$$\alpha \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{A}{2}, \quad \beta \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{B}{2}, \quad \gamma \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{C}{2}, \quad \delta \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{D}{2} \quad \text{ёки} \quad \alpha \Rightarrow \frac{A}{2}, \quad \beta \Rightarrow \frac{B}{2}, \quad \gamma \Rightarrow \frac{C}{2},$$

$$\delta \Rightarrow \frac{D}{2}.$$

In this case it is possible to form a mirror through the corners at the ends of an arbitrary rectangle, or $A + B + C + D = 2\pi$ since:

$$\sin A + \sin B + \sin C + \sin D = 4\sin \frac{A+B}{2} \cdot \sin \frac{A+C}{2} \cdot \sin \frac{B+C}{2}.$$

The latter is expressing interesting planimetric content through trigonometric relations, as are triangles.

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